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Enhancing teacher collaboration for technology integration: the impact of transformational leadership

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Transformational leadership
Teacher collaboration
Technology integration
Upper-secondary education
Empirical paper

ABSTRACT

The study explored how school principals' transformational leadership impacts formal and informal teacher collaboration for technology integration. Goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration in Swiss upper-secondary schools were considered as mediators. Analyzing data from a survey of 2247 teachers using multilevel correlation and structural equation modeling (SEM) with cluster-robust standard errors, we found that principals' transformational leadership is significantly and positively correlated with both formal and informal teacher collaboration, goal clarity, and strategic importance of technology integration. Further, SEM analysis revealed that transformational leadership has a significant, positive, and direct effect on formal collaboration but has only a significant indirect effect on informal collaboration. Moreover, the strategic importance of technology integration mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and formal collaboration as well as informal collaboration. However, goal clarity was only a significant mediator for the relationship between transformational leadership and informal collaboration. These findings suggest that for effective technology integration, school principals should prioritize transformational leadership to ensure a high strategic importance and goal clarity regarding technology integration which in turn have a positive impact on formal and informal collaboration.

1. Introduction

Various studies have found that teacher collaboration significantly and positively promotes technology integration in schools (Cattaneo et al., 2025; Blau & Shamir-Inbal, 2017; Guggemos & Seufert, 2021; Hatlevik & Hatlevik, 2018a, b; Inan & Lowther, 2010; Lorenz et al., 2019; Prasse, 2012; Petko et al., 2018). Technology integration can be described as the use of technology by teachers to achieve educational goals or the process leading to these educational aims (Consoli et al., 2023). Thus, the present study aims to identify predictors of teacher collaboration in technology integration. Within the scope of this, a model was investigated with transformational leadership enacted by the school leader as a predictor of teacher collaboration in technology integration and strategic importance of technology integration as well as goal clarity regarding technology integration as mediators.

Teacher collaboration can be defined as a joint group interaction in all activities needed to perform a shared task (Hargreaves,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2025.105331>

Received 17 October 2024; Received in revised form 19 March 2025; Accepted 21 April 2025

Available online 21 April 2025

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2021; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Weddle, 2022). In contrast to collegiality, the focus is not on relationships among teachers at the same school but on collaborative work-related activities. Collaboration can be considered an umbrella term for different collaborative concepts, and different types of collaboration can occur among teachers (Hargreaves, 2021; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Weddle, 2022). A very common distinction is between formal and informal collaboration (see Hargreaves, 2021; Petko et al., 2018). Whereas formal collaboration refers to the school establishing a suitable environment and formally encouraging teachers to cooperate, informal collaboration relates to spontaneous initiatives and collaborative activities by teachers (Petko et al., 2018). Moreover, teacher collaboration is a continuum. The following criteria decide the position of the collaboration form on the continuum: shared goals and responsibilities, task cohesion (shared commitment to the task), identification with the team, task interdependence (needing each other to fulfill a task), and goal interdependence (needing each other to accomplish a goal) (Vangrieken et al., 2015).

It has become evident that teacher collaboration not only fosters teaching quality and student achievement, as numerous studies have shown (Hargreaves, 2021; Reeves et al., 2017; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Weddle, 2022), but it could also be helpful in achieving common goals for technology integration in schools. Some studies have shown that collaborative activities promote higher levels of technology integration. For example, Inan and Lowther (2010) indicated that peer support from other teachers regarding digital technologies is a significant and positive predictor of teachers' readiness to use digital technologies and teachers' beliefs about digital technologies, which in turn have a significant and positive influence on technology integration operationalized as the frequency of teachers integrating technology into their instruction. This is challenged by another study indicating that inter- and intra-school teacher collaboration was not a significant predictor of school culture with a focus on technology integration (Blau & Shamir-Inbal, 2017). Guggemos and Seufert (2021) found that teacher collaboration knowledge, measured as teachers' self-efficacy to collaborate through digital technologies with other teachers to promote technology integration in school, is significantly and positively correlated with teachers' use of digital technologies in class and teaching about digital technologies in class. Moreover, teacher collaboration is significantly and positively correlated with the frequency of teachers using digital technologies for various instructional purposes and their self-efficacy in teaching with digital technologies in class (Hatlevik & Hatlevik, 2018a, 2018b). Furthermore, teacher collaboration was found to be a significant and positive predictor of teachers fostering students' computer and information literacy (Lorenz et al., 2019). Prasse (2012) found that teachers' formal and informal collaboration, goal clarity in technology integration, and the strategic importance of technology integration in the school strategy play key roles in effective technology integration. This finding was confirmed by Petko et al. (2018), who showed that formal and informal collaboration, together with goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration in the school strategy, significantly and positively predict technology integration.

Despite the growing body of evidence stressing the importance of teacher collaboration for technology integration, studies that identify the factors that influence teachers' formal and informal collaboration in technology integration are still lacking. Identifying factors with positive impacts on general teacher collaboration could help draw conclusions about collaboration in relation to technology integration. In their systematic review, De Jong et al. (2022) identified six categories of factors that predict general teacher collaboration: personal, group, process, guidance, structural, and organizational factors. Whereas personal factors address teachers' attitudes, beliefs, knowledge, skills, and professional identity, the group factor relates to group atmosphere heterogeneity and experience. Process factors refer to aspects such as collectiveness (having a shared goal) and the focus on a specific teaching aspect. By contrast, guidance factors reflect facilitation by external support of the collaboration group and feedback. Structural factors encompass administrative support and a professionalization structure. Lastly, organizational factors are related to school atmosphere, recognition of collaboration efforts, shared vision and goals, priorities of the schools regarding educational aspects, and school leadership (De Jong et al., 2022). The systematic review by García-Martínez et al. (2021) focused on a school development perspective and stressed the role of the organizational factors and the school leader in fostering general teacher collaboration. Thus, there is consensus among studies that next to organizational factors such as goal clarity and educational priorities of the schools, principals can have a great influence on teacher collaboration through their leadership style (De Jong et al., 2022; García-Martínez et al., 2021; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Weddle, 2022).

One leadership style that might promote teacher collaboration is transformational leadership. Studies have indicated that transformational leadership significantly and positively promotes professional learning communities, which is a concept close to teacher collaboration (see Valckx et al., 2020; Voelkel, 2022). Moreover, transformational leadership also significantly and positively affects other proxies of teacher collaboration, such as task interdependence (Beverborg et al., 2015). Furthermore, transformational leadership significantly and positively influences teacher collaboration regarding specific goals, such as individualized education planning (Lambrecht et al., 2022) and differentiated instruction (Ninković et al., 2022). Transformational leadership has also a significant and positive impact on general teacher collaboration (Fernandes et al., 2022; Lucas & Valentine, 2002). However, thus far, no study has investigated the effect of transformational leadership on teacher collaboration within the context of technology integration. In the next section, we present our argument on why transformational leadership might also be a significant and positive predictor of teacher collaboration, with the specific goal of fostering technology integration at school.

1.1. Transformational leadership and teacher collaboration in technology integration

Similar to teacher collaboration, several researchers have postulated that leadership could be an important factor influencing successful technology integration in schools (Chiu, 2022; Dexter, 2018; Dexter & Richardson, 2020; Eickelmann, 2011; Fisher & Waller, 2013; Hadjithoma-Garstka, 2011; Håkansson Lindqvist, 2019; Harder et al., 2020; Krein, 2023). However, different leadership practices seem to have a positive impact on technology integration (see Tan, 2010). Various studies have indicated that schools with complementary bottom-up and top-down approaches are the most successful in school innovations and integrating technology (Petko et al., 2015; Dexter, 2008, pp. 543–554; Fullan, 1994, pp. 7–24). In particular, Petko et al. (2015) showed that schools with

complementary bottom-up and top-down activities enable students to use technology more significantly. These findings suggest that leadership behavior, which is a combination of bottom-up and top-down approaches, might have a positive influence on technology integration.

One influential research stream of leadership research that deals with a combination of complementary bottom-up and top-down approaches is transformational leadership. Although transformational leadership is often characterized as a bottom-up approach in the literature (Daniëls et al., 2019), it is a combination of strong bottom-up practices carried out by the principal, such as staff development, supportive leadership, and empowerment, to foster innovative thinking and support top-down activities, such as providing a vision, charismatic leadership and leading by example (Ruloff & Petko, 2021; Schmitz et al., 2023). Originally, Bass (1990) postulated that transformational leadership consists of the components of idealized influence (providing a sense and mission, instilling pride, and gaining respect), inspiration (communicating high expectations and expressing important aspects in simple ways), intellectual stimulation (promoting rationality and careful problem-solving), and individual consideration (giving each employee personal attention, coaching, and advising). Carless et al. (2000) and Podsakoff et al. (1990) operationalize transformational leadership by measuring the following components: vision that is similar to Bass (1990) conceptualization of inspiration, staff development and supportive leadership referring to individual consideration, empowerment by promoting cooperation between employees, innovative thinking that is related to intellectual stimulation, leading by example and charismatic leadership similar to individualized influence described by Bass (1990). However, Bass (1990) stressed the role of a charismatic leader, whereas more recent research on transformational leadership in an educational context has shifted from leader characteristics to leadership practices carried out by school leaders, such as providing a vision, fostering collaboration, leading by example, individual support, and motivating the school staff toward a goal (Anderson, 2017; Daniëls et al., 2019; Ottestad, 2013). These practices overlap with the duties of school principals to promote technology integration in schools in particular, identifying a shared vision and communicating this vision, developing the people by appreciating and supporting the individual, leading by example, and building a collaborative culture (see Dexter, 2018; Dexter & Richardson, 2020; Håkansson Lindqvist, 2019; Tulowitzki et al., 2022). Yuen et al. (2003) concluded that shifting from automating tasks and school processes with digital technologies to rethinking education fundamentally by using technology and redesigning school processes requires transformational leadership.

Consistently, numerous studies have shown that transformational leadership is a positive predictor of teachers' technology integration in class (Chen, 2013; Ng, 2008; Ottestad, 2013; Schmitz et al., 2023; Vermeulen et al., 2015; Vermeulen et al., 2017; Yamamoto & Yamaguchi, 2019). Moreover, Petko et al. (2018) and Ninković et al. (2023) suggested that leadership must be seen in the context of other aspects of school readiness to integrate technology and innovation, such as formal and informal teacher collaboration, goal clarity regarding digital technologies, and the importance of technology integration in school strategy. Several studies have already revealed that transformational leadership is significantly and positively correlated with teacher collaboration regarding a broad range of school development tasks (Beverbourg et al., 2015; Fernandes et al., 2022; Lambrecht et al., 2022; Lucas & Valentine, 2002; Ninković et al., 2022; Valckx et al., 2020; Voelkel, 2022).

Numerous studies indicated that transformational leadership enacted by the school leader is a significant and positive predictor for different proxies for teacher collaboration. For example, the longitudinal study with Dutch vocational education teachers by Beverbourg et al. (2015) revealed that transformational leadership operationalized as individualized consideration and intellectual stimulation carried out by school leaders had a significant and positive effect on task interdependence which can be considered a proxy of teacher collaboration. Similarly, the study by Valckx et al. (2020) based on 324 Flemish secondary-school teachers showed that transformational leadership has a significant, direct positive effect on collective responsibility as a characteristic of a professional learning community that also serves as a proxy for teacher collaboration. Moreover, transformational leadership had a significant, positive but only indirect effect on reflective dialogue as another characteristic of a professional learning community. In line with these findings, the study by Voelkel (2022) with American K-6 school teachers indicated that components of transformational leadership such as inspiring a shared vision have a significant and positive impact on professional learning communities that are characterized by collective goals and actions as well as a focus on results. In contrast to previous findings, the component leading by example of transformational leadership has detrimental effects on professional learning communities.

Moreover, there is also evidence that transformational leadership not only promotes different proxies of teacher collaboration but also teacher collaboration itself: The study by Fernandes et al. (2022) showed that transformational leadership with its components intellectual stimulation and charisma has a significant and positive impact on teachers' professional collaboration. By contrast, the study by Lucas and Valentine (2002) revealed that intellectual stimulation was not a significant predictor for general teacher collaboration. However, other components of transformational leadership such as providing a vision and individual support are significant and positive predictors for teacher collaboration. Contrary to the study by Voelkel (2022) leading by example was also a significant and positive predictor for teacher collaboration. Similar patterns cannot only be identified for teacher collaboration in general but also for teacher collaboration with a specific goal: For example, Lambrecht et al. (2022) found that transformational leadership reported by German school leaders significantly and positively affected collaboration structures which in turn significantly and positively influence the implementation of individualized education planning. Furthermore, transformational leadership had a stronger effect on collaboration structures than instructional leadership in this study. The study by Ninković et al. (2022) based on 314 Serbian teachers indicated that vision building, individual consideration, and intellectual stimulation as three dimensions of transformational leadership significantly and positively influenced differentiated instruction via teacher collaboration. Given that transformational leadership fosters teacher collaboration for individualized education planning and differentiated instruction, this leadership style might also promote teacher collaboration in technology integration.

Regarding technology integration in particular, some studies have provided empirical evidence that transformational school principals seem to be more in favor of digital technology and use it more often than principals with other leadership practices (Afshari

et al., 2009; Arokiasamy et al., 2015; Laouni, 2020; Seyal, 2015; Tan, 2010). These findings were supported by Miranda and Russell (2011), who indicated that principals' use of technology has a positive influence on teacher-directed student use of technology. Thus, it is not surprising that transformational school leaders tend to have a positive attitude toward technology use to promote innovation and hold strong positive beliefs about digital technology (Laschou et al., 2018). This also fits the perspective of transformational leadership as a change-oriented leadership behavior (Derue et al., 2011).

In line with this conclusion, a qualitative case study found that transformational leadership is significantly and positively correlated with digital change at the school level and clear goals for digital learning and literacy (Ruloff & Petko, 2021). Transformational school leaders with these characteristics might be inclined to promote teacher collaboration concerning technology integration and they create an environment with clear goals and a high priority of technology integration that supports the teamwork of teachers regarding technology integration. Consequently, it would be worthwhile for a quantitative study to examine whether transformational leadership enacted by the school principal has a significant and positive effect on formal and informal teacher collaboration in technology integration. In this case, it would be important to incorporate all subdimensions of transformational that were examined in previous studies such as vision, individual consideration, and intellectual stimulation. Leadership by example should also be included as a sub-dimension, as the current study situation does not clearly show whether this component has positive or negative effects on teacher collaboration (Lucas & Valentine, 2002; Voelkel, 2022). However, various studies indicate that transformational leadership has a rather indirect effect on the behavior of teachers such as collaboration in technology integration (see Valckx et al., 2020; Vermeulen et al., 2015; Vermeulen et al., 2017). Hence, the following section proposes possible mediators of the relationship between transformational leadership and formal as well as informal teacher collaboration in technology integration.

1.2. Goal clarity and strategic importance of technology integration as mediators of the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher collaboration in technology integration

As several studies have indicated that formal and informal collaboration in technology integration also depend on the goal clarity in technology integration and the importance of technology integration in the school strategy (Cattaneo et al., 2025; Petko et al., 2018; Prasse, 2012), goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration should be mediators of the relationship between transformational leadership and informal collaboration as well as formal collaboration. According to Prasse (2012) goal clarity in technology integration means that the school staff has a shared vision regarding teaching with digital technologies. Moreover, this construct includes commitment to common goals of ICT-supported teaching. By contrast, strategic importance of technology integration is related to perceived appreciation and support of new ideas, practices, and technologies. This construct mirrors whether technology integration is a priority in the school (Prasse, 2012). Clear goals and a high strategic importance of technology integration might foster teacher collaboration in technology integration since teachers have a shared vision of technology use for teaching when exchanging ideas and feel appreciated for cooperating on projects of technology integration. This claim is supported by previous studies stressing the importance of organizational predictors for teacher collaboration such as goal clarity and educational priorities of schools (De Jong et al., 2022; García-Martínez et al., 2021; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Weddle, 2022). Regarding the strategic importance as a potential predictor for teacher collaboration in technology integration, De Jong et al. (2022) reported in their literature review that educational priorities were found to be crucial for sharing and experimenting as teacher collaboration activities in several studies. Moreover, recognition that mirrors the appreciation of the school for the teachers' effort for a common goal was also an important enabler for experimenting. Regarding goal clarity as a potential predictor for teacher collaboration, De Jong et al. (2022) indicated a shared mission (goals) was identified as important for the teacher collaboration activity of sharing. Fittingly, the literature review by Vangrieken et al. (2015) identified a shared meaning that overlaps with the concept of goal clarity as an important facilitator for teacher collaboration. In line with this, the study by Lucas and Valentine (2002) revealed that fostering commitment to goals promotes teacher collaboration. Given that transformational leadership carried out by the school leader has only an indirect effect on teacher behavior, goal clarity and strategic importance of technology integration (educational priority) might mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and teacher collaboration in technology integration.

1.3. Hypothesis

Taking into account earlier findings, the present study proposes the following hypotheses, as illustrated in the conceptual model of Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Conceptual model.

- (1) Transformational leadership is significantly and positively correlated with formal collaboration and informal collaboration in technology integration.
- (2) Transformational leadership is significantly and positively correlated with goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration.
- (3) Transformational leadership is a significant and positive predictor of formal collaboration and informal collaboration in technology integration
- (4) Goal clarity and strategic importance significantly mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and informal collaboration
- (5) Goal clarity and strategic importance significantly mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and formal collaboration

2. Methods

2.1. Participants and procedure

In this study, all Swiss upper-secondary schools were contacted to invite all Swiss teachers who taught in the second and third grades of an upper-secondary school to participate in an online survey in the canton of Zurich from September 20 to November 8, 2021, and in the other cantons from May 1 to August 1, 2022. Overall, 2248 teachers from 113 schools completed the online questionnaire. One case was removed from the analyses as one school was only represented by one teacher, leading to a final sample of 2247 teachers in 112 clusters (schools). Regarding gender, 50.5 % of teachers considered themselves male, 47.3 % indicated being female, and 2.2 % chose the option “other”. In our sample, 79.2 % of the teachers were employed in a Swiss school in the German-speaking part, 11.3 % of teachers were employed in a school in the Italian-speaking region of Switzerland, and 9.5 % of teachers were employed in a school in the French-speaking region. Regarding school type, 41.8 % of teachers reported teaching in a general education school, 40.7 % in a vocational education school, and 17.5 % in schools that combine vocational education and general education.

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. Transformational leadership

Transformational leadership was measured using the exact wording of the global transformational leadership scale with seven items from [Carless et al. \(2000\)](#). Several international studies have confirmed the scale’s reliability, validity, and unidimensionality (see, e.g., [Ghadi et al., 2013](#); [Gillet et al., 2013](#); [Munir et al., 2010](#); [Scheel et al., 2019](#); [van Beveren et al., 2017](#)). To avoid confounding transformational leadership with teacher collaboration regarding technology integration, teachers were asked to rate how often their school leaders engage in typical forms of transformational leadership behavior independently of technology use. Each of the seven items represents one of those typical leadership behaviors (all items and the corresponding leadership behaviors are listed in the appendix). The answer options on the Likert scale ranged from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The scale shows satisfactory fit values after a confirmatory factor analysis and good reliability (For more details on the results of the scale with this sample, see [Schmitz et al., 2023](#)).

2.2.2. Formal collaboration, informal collaboration, goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration

Formal collaboration, informal collaboration, goal clarity, and the strategic importance of technology integration were measured with three items, following [Petko et al. \(2018\)](#). The answer options ranged from 1 (totally disagree) to 5 (totally agree). Formal collaboration (e.g., “We often hold internal school information events on the use of digital technologies in the classroom”) has good reliability, with a Cronbach’s α of .80 and a McDonald’s ω of .81. The reliability of informal collaboration (e.g., “We discuss very intensively our experiences regarding the possible uses of digital technologies”) was also considered good, with .78 for Cronbach’s α and McDonald’s ω . Similarly, goal clarity of technology integration (“goal clarity of technology integration”, sample item: “I am clear about my school’s goals for digital technology use”) has good reliability, with .76 for Cronbach’s α and McDonald’s ω . Lastly, the scale strategic importance of technology integration (“strategic importance of technology integration”, sample item: “The topic of digitization is very important at our school”) also showed good reliability, with .79 for Cronbach’s α and .80 for McDonald’s ω . More details on the single items can be found in the appendix.

After five modifications, which allow for residual covariances between items, the CFA shows a good fit ($\chi^2(43) = 403$; $p < .001$; TLI = .953; CFI = .969; RMSEA = .061; SRMR = .027). According to [Hu and Bentler \(1999\)](#) and [Brown \(2015\)](#), TLI and CFI values higher than .95 indicate a good fit, while the RSMEA and SRMR values lower than .08 represent a good fit. Moreover, we found that all items of the scales transformational leadership, formal collaboration, informal collaboration, goal clarity of technology integration, and strategic importance of technology integration had a skewness < 2 and a kurtosis < 7 , indicating that their use would be appropriate for structural equation modeling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation (see [Curran et al., 1996](#)).

2.3. Statistical analyses

2.3.1. Descriptive statistics

Means and standard deviations were calculated for the constructs of transformational leadership, formal collaboration, informal collaboration, goal clarity, and the strategic importance of technology integration. The descriptive analyses were carried out with weighted data, as a full survey of the population was not achieved, and we had obtained an uneven distribution of the sample regarding

school responses, school type, and language region (Kish & Frankel, 1974; Meinck, 2015, pp. 1–13; Schmitz et al., 2023).

2.3.2. Inferential statistics

For all inferential statistics, unweighted data were used, since weighted data tend to distort the results of these analyses (Gelman, 2007; Winship & Radbill, 1994).

To test the first and second hypotheses, multilevel correlations were conducted considering the nested data, and the multilevel correlation coefficients were interpreted according to Cohen (1992): $r > .10$ are weak effects, correlations with $r > .30$ are moderate effects, and correlations with $r = > .50$ are strong effects.

To test the other hypotheses, SEM with cluster-robust standard errors was conducted (see Oberski, 2014; Stapleton et al., 2016). Since the teachers' perception of school leadership and formal collaboration, informal collaboration, goal clarity, and strategic importance of technology integration seem to have individual effects on the teacher level rather than the school level (see, e.g., Ninković et al., 2023), SEM with cluster-robust standard errors seems to be more suitable than a multilevel SEM, which also requires school-level predictors. Moreover, we do not have enough clusters and sample size power to perform multilevel SEM mediation analysis (McNeish, 2017; Zigler & Ye, 2019). An SEM was performed with the latent construct of transformational leadership as a predictor of formal collaboration, and informal collaboration, whereas, goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration were the mediators of the model. As typically three to four items per latent variable are ideal for achieving a good model fit and transformational leadership is a latent variable with seven items, item parceling was conducted to enable SEM with cluster-robust standard errors (see Little et al., 2013). The item parceling was performed based on theoretical considerations calculating the mean value of items similar in content (for the exact item parceling procedure with this scale see Schmitz et al., 2023).

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics depicted in Table 1 show that teachers rated the transformational leadership carried out by their school leader as the highest of all variables, whereas informal collaboration had the lowest mean. Teachers' formal and informal collaboration in technology integration showed a high variation, which is explained by subsequent analyses.

3.2. Multilevel correlations

Multilevel correlation analyses as presented in Table 2 revealed that transformational leadership was significantly correlated with formal collaboration, informal collaboration, goal clarity, and the strategic importance of technology integration. The correlations were categorized as moderate. Furthermore, the correlations between formal and informal collaboration, goal clarity, and strategic importance were strong, except for the correlation between formal collaboration and goal clarity, which was classified as moderate. All correlations remained significant after the Bonferroni correction.

3.3. Structural equation modelling with cluster-robust standard errors

The SEM model with cluster-robust standard errors with transformational leadership as a predictor formal and informal collaboration as outcome variables and goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration as the mediators showed a good fit ($\chi^2(88) = 637.945$; $p < .001$; TLI = .964; CFI = .951; RMSEA = .060; SRMR = .037), with six modifications. All factor loadings of the latent variables (transformational leadership, formal collaboration, informal collaboration, goal clarity, and strategic importance) were ≥ 0.60 and could be categorized as strong (Garson, 2009). The analysis illustrated in Fig. 2 revealed that transformational leadership had a significant, small, and direct effect on formal collaboration but the direct effect on informal collaboration was not significant. Moreover, transformational leadership had a significant and positive impact on goal clarity and strategic importance. The predictor transformational leadership explained 32.7 % of the variance in goal clarity and 20.3 % of the variance in strategic importance. As depicted in Fig. 2, strategic importance is a significant mediator of the relationships between transformational leadership and formal collaboration ($\beta = .72$, $p < .001$) as well as informal collaboration ($\beta = .49$, $p < .001$). Goal clarity significantly mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and informal collaboration ($\beta = .32$, $p < .001$). However, goal clarity is not a significant mediator of the relationship between transformational leadership and formal collaboration ($\beta = .03$, $p = .788$). This is

Table 1
Descriptive statistics.

	Mean	SD
Transformational leadership	3.69	0.95
Formal collaboration for technology integration	2.94	1.06
Informal collaboration for technology integration	2.60	0.97
Goal clarity of technology integration	2.96	0.99
Strategic importance of technology integration	3.55	0.98

Note. Means and standard deviations (SD) are weighted.

Table 2
Results of the multilevel correlation analyses.

Variable 1	Variable 2	r	p	CI Lower	CI Upper
leadership	formal collaboration	.36	<.001	.33	.40
leadership	informal collaboration	.33	<.001	.29	.37
leadership	strategic importance	.38	<.001	.35	.42
leadership	goal clarity	.45	<.001	.42	.48
formal collaboration	informal collaboration	.52	<.001	.48	.54
formal collaboration	strategic importance	.51	<.001	.48	.54
formal collaboration	goal clarity	.47	<.001	.44	.50
informal collaboration	strategic importance	.50	<.001	.47	.53
informal collaboration	goal clarity	.50	<.001	.46	.53
strategic importance	goal clarity	.54	<.001	.51	.57

Note. N = 2247, df = 2245, CI = confidence interval.

Fig. 2. Structural Equation model.

Note. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$. Standardized path coefficients and covariances between latent variables and the variances explained by the endogenous variables are presented. The measurement models are not depicted in this figure.

also mirrored by Table 3 indicating that the indirect effect of strategic importance is significant for formal and informal collaboration, whereas the indirect effect of goal clarity is only significant for informal collaboration. Furthermore, the total effects on formal and informal collaboration are significant. Regarding formal collaboration 61.5 % of the variance could be explained by the other variables of the model, whereas 58.3 % of the variance in informal collaboration could be explained by the model.

4. Discussion

4.1. Summary of the results

As transformational leadership was significantly, positively, and moderately correlated with formal and informal collaboration for technology integration, the first hypothesis was supported. These findings strengthen the claim that school leaders play an important role in teacher collaboration (García-Martínez et al., 2020; Jong et al., 2022; Vangrieken et al., 2015; Weddle, 2022). Previous studies indicate that transformational leadership has a significant and positive relationship with general teacher collaboration (Fernandes et al., 2022; Lucas et al., 2002) and teacher collaboration with the specific goal of instruction differentiation or individualized education planning (Lambrecht et al., 2022; Ninković et al., 2022). The study extends these previous findings by showing that transformational leadership has also a significant and positive relationship with collaboration in the context of technology integration. The second hypothesis was also supported, as transformational leadership was significantly and positively correlated with goal clarity and the strategic importance of technology integration in schools.

The third hypothesis that transformational leadership is a significant and positive predictor of formal and informal collaboration was only partially confirmed since SEM analysis showed that transformational leadership significantly and directly influences formal

Table 3
Standardized indirect and total effects.

	Estimate	SE	p	CI lower	CI upper
Indirect effect goal clarity on informal collaboration	.18	.05	.001	.08	.29
Indirect effect strategic importance on informal collaboration	.22	.04	.000	.14	.30
Total effect on informal collaboration	.38	.03	.000	.33	.44
Indirect effect goal clarity on formal collaboration	.02	.07	.788	-.11	.15
Indirect effect strategic importance on formal collaboration	.33	.05	.000	.22	.43
Total effect on formal collaboration	.33	.04	.000	.25	.40

Note. Standard errors (SE) are cluster robust, CI = confidence interval.

collaboration but not informal collaboration. This can be explained by the fact that informal collaboration mostly relies on the initiative of the teachers and can only be addressed by the school principal to a limited extent. These findings align with the study by Valckx et al. (2020) showing that transformational leadership has a direct effect on some aspects of teacher collaboration and an indirect effect on informal exchange and dialogue of teachers. Still, this study indicates that transformational leadership has a direct significant, and positive effect on formal teacher collaboration supporting the evidence from previous studies (Fernandes et al., 2022; Lambrecht et al., 2022; Lucas & Valentine, 2002; Ninković et al., 2022). However, the significant, direct, and positive effect of transformational leadership including the aspect of leading by example contradicts the findings by Voelkel (2020) that some components of transformational leadership such as leading by example can have detrimental effects on teacher collaboration.

Moreover, the analysis showed that transformational leadership is a significant and positive predictor of goal clarity and strategic importance with a substantial degree of variance explanation. This aligns with the theoretical perspective of transformational leaders who engage in providing their team with a clear vision and mission for the organization (Anderson, 2017; Daniëls et al., 2019; Ottestad, 2013). Fittingly, Ruloff and Petko (2021) showed that transformational leaders are able to set clearer goals for learning with digital technologies and digital literacy than principals with different leadership behaviors. Furthermore, the fourth and the fifth hypothesis stating that goal clarity and strategic importance of technology integration are significant mediators for the relationship between transformational leadership and formal collaboration as well as informal collaboration were only partially confirmed. The strategic importance of technology integration significantly mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and formal collaboration as well as informal collaboration. These findings align with several studies stressing that priorities of specific educational aspects in schools are one of the most important organizational predictors for teacher collaboration (De Jong et al., 2022; Mon et al., 2016; Vangrieken et al., 2015). In line with previous studies indicating that a shared vision and common goals are important organizational factors influencing teacher collaboration (De Jong et al., 2022; Truijen et al., 2013; Vangrieken et al., 2015) goal clarity in technology integration is a significant mediator for the relationship between transformational leadership and informal collaboration. However, goal clarity does not significantly mediate the relationship between transformational leadership and formal collaboration. This could be due to the fact that formal collaboration is more strongly structured by the school leader. Informal collaboration, on the other hand, is more the responsibility of the teachers, which is why they need to be clearer about the goals. Moreover, De Jong et al. (2022) pointed out that educational priorities and recognition that overlap with the concept of strategic importance of technology integration is crucial for sharing and experimenting as teacher collaboration activities. However, a shared mission that relates to the construct of goal clarity regarding technology integration was only relevant for sharing. Goal clarity could be considered a matter of fact since the goal is already defined and has just to be shared whereas, strategic importance of technology integration also involves a co-constructed process demanding more active participation of the teachers. In the case of formal collaboration, the clear communication of the school leader might be sufficient and no provision of clear goals is needed whereas strategic importance is still crucial to ensure other collaboration activities beyond sharing information. By contrast, for informal collaboration clear goals are needed for collaborative sharing activities due to the limited influence of the school leader and strategic importance is relevant to facilitate other collaboration activities such as experimenting. Overall, this study shows that organizational factors such as transformational leadership, goal clarity, and strategic importance of technology integration can explain a substantial amount of variance in formal (61.5 %) and informal collaboration (58.3 %) regarding technology integration. This is consistent with the literature review by García-Martínez et al. (2021), which adopts a school development perspective and emphasizes the relevance of organizational factors.

4.2. Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, school principals, instead of teachers, could have been surveyed for their leadership behavior to avoid mono-source bias. However, previous studies have shown that principals tend to rate their leadership practices much more positively than teachers and respond in socially desirable ways (see, e.g., Imboden et al., 2020). In addition, the integration of transformational leadership from the perspective of the school leaders would warrant a multilevel SEM mediation analysis, for which our sample does not have enough clusters (McNeish, 2017; Zigler & Ye, 2019). Second, the global transformational leadership scale by Carless et al. (2000) stresses leadership characteristics such as charisma, whereas more recent measurements focus on leadership practices instead of characteristics. However, for reasons of instrument acceptability by teachers and time efficiency, we preferred the short scale by Carless et al. (2000) with only seven items to the more up-to-date measurement instruments with substantially more items. As this study does not have an experimental design where, for example, the leadership style is experimentally manipulated in different groups, no causal statements can be made. Moreover, for mediation analyses longitudinal data is preferable to cross-sectional data since this allows to track the effects of the predictors and the mediating variables over time (Maxwell & Cole, 2007). Furthermore, this study focuses only on transformational leadership instead of comparing different leadership behaviors, such as distributed and instructional leadership, to identify the most suitable.

Although item parceling can be considered a controversial technique, it was used in this study to perform SEM (see Little et al., 2013; Marsh et al., 2013). In this particular case, however, it must be added that the unidimensionality of the scale has been confirmed several times (for example, see Ghadi et al., 2013; Gillet et al., 2013; Munir et al., 2010; Scheel et al., 2019; van Beveren et al., 2017), which somewhat defuses the problem of the procedure. Additionally, the parcels were formed based on theoretical considerations, which is preferable to parcels formed only to achieve statistical advantages (Little et al., 2013; Marsh et al., 2013). As only upper secondary school teachers from Switzerland took part in this study, these results can only be generalized to a very limited extent and it remains questionable what effects are present in other school levels or countries.

4.3. Directions for future research and practical implications

This study leaves several questions open that could be investigated in future research. For example, we did not compare the effects of alternative leadership behaviors on teachers' formal and informal collaborations. As [Petko et al. \(2015\)](#) found that purely top-down approaches are also very effective for technology integration in schools, a top-down leadership practice, such as instructional leadership with its components communicating a vision, focusing on the instructional program and professional development (see [Daniëls et al., 2019](#)) might also be an effective way to foster teacher collaboration in technology integration. For example, there is also evidence that an instructional leadership style enacted by the school principal significantly and positively predicts teacher collaboration in general ([Goddard et al., 2015](#); [Gumus et al., 2013](#); [Lambrecht et al., 2022](#); [Liu, Bellibas et al., 2021](#); [Mora-Ruano et al., 2021](#)). Instructional leadership includes components of communicating a vision and focusing on the instructional program (setting educational priorities), the school's learning climate, and professional development (see [Daniëls et al., 2019](#); [Hallinger, 2003](#)). Instructional leaders that communicate a clear vision and prioritize pedagogical aspects in the instructional program might also foster the strategic importance of technology integration and goal clarity at their school which in turn would positively affect informal and formal collaboration. Fittingly, the study by [Eickelmann \(2011\)](#) showed that school leaders with a comprehensive understanding of the potential of ICT to enhance learning that is related to an instructional leadership style managed to establish clear ICT concepts and clear pedagogical goals with a high priority.

Moreover, various qualitative studies indicate that a rather bottom-up approach, such as distributed leadership, might have positive effects on technology integration or technology-related innovation processes in a school ([Divaharan & Ping, 2010](#); [Hauge & Norenes, 2015](#); [Ng Foo Seong & Ho, 2012](#); [Schrum & Levin, 2013](#)). Many studies have shown that distributed leadership directly, significantly, and positively affects teacher collaboration in general ([García Torres, 2019](#); [Liu, Bellibas et al., 2021](#); [Liu, Keeley et al., 2021](#)). Thus, adopting distributed leadership practices might also be helpful for principals when they aim to promote formal and informal collaboration in technology integration. Regarding mediators between distributed leadership and teacher collaboration, it might be worthwhile to consider again strategic importance of technology integration and goal clarity. There is qualitative evidence indicating that in schools with clear goals regarding digital technologies and a high importance of technology integration, the school leader applies a distributive leadership style ([Divaharan & Ping, 2010](#); [Schrum & Levin, 2013](#)).

Furthermore, we had only cross-sectional data; therefore, it is unclear whether transformational leadership has different effects on formal and informal collaboration in different phases of the technology integration process in schools. Moreover, this study leaves open the role that inter-teacher dynamics play in the effect of transformational leadership on teacher collaboration in technology integration. It might be interesting to investigate whether transformational leadership promotes teacher collaboration when teachers are in favor of or against technology-related changes at their schools.

In terms of practical implications, this study provides empirical evidence that transformational leadership practices of school leaders might help foster goal clarity, the strategic importance of technology integration, and teacher collaboration. This means that school leaders should engage in different forms of transformational leadership behavior: They should communicate a clear and positive vision for the future. Moreover, school leaders should prioritize staff development, support their teachers, and facilitate cooperation among teachers. Furthermore, school leaders should encourage the teachers to think innovatively, lead by example, and apply a charismatic leadership style. Since various studies have shown that training is conducive to developing transformational leadership behavior (see, e.g., [Brown & May 2012](#); [Cohrs et al., 2020](#); [Kelloway et al., 2000](#)), it could be advisable for school principals to take part in such training opportunities when they intend to lead in a transformational way to improve teacher collaboration in technology integration. Another key finding is that strategic importance of technology integration significantly and positively influences teachers' formal and informal collaboration, whereas goal clarity is only a significant and positive predictor for teachers' informal collaboration. Hence, school leaders should be aware that prioritizing technology integration as an educational goal is important for teachers' formal and informal collaboration. For formal collaboration strategic importance and engagement in transformational leadership are sufficient. By contrast, clear goals need to be established for informal collaboration as this cannot be as well-structured and influenced by the school leader as formal collaboration. Overall this study shows that transformational leadership is helpful to foster teacher collaboration and illustrates differential effects on formal and informal collaboration.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maria-Luisa Schmitz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Chiara Antonietti:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Tessa Consoli:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Philipp Gonon:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Alberto Cattaneo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Dominik Petko:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation and related to project number 407740_182727.

Our study complies with the ethical standards of the Swiss Academy of Social Sciences and Humanities.

Appendix

Construct	Item	Mean	SD	α if deleted	Item discrimination
Transformational leadership	The school leader ...				
Vision	... communicates a clear and positive vision of the future.	3.85	0.97	.95	.72
Staff development	... treats staff as individuals, supports, and encourages their development.	3.95	1.02	.94	.85
Supportive leadership	... gives encouragement and recognition to staff.	3.84	1.07	.94	.86
Empowerment	... fosters trust, involvement, and cooperation among team members.	3.72	1.08	.94	.87
Innovative thinking	... encourages thinking about problems in new ways and questions assumptions.	3.52	1.06	.94	.81
Leading by example	... is clear about his/her values and practices what he/she preaches.	3.70	1.08	.94	.84
Charismatic leadership	... instills pride and respect in others and inspires me by being highly competent.	3.45	1.16	.94	.85
Formal collaboration	Please indicate how you rate the following statements for your school.				
	It often happens that colleagues present something on the topic technology use in class (e.g., in conferences, through notices).	3.19	1.18	.72	.66
	We often hold internal school information events on technology use in class.	3.36	1.19	.67	.70
	We often exchange experiences with digital technologies with external partners/schools (e.g., invitations to lectures, excursions).	2.40	1.16	.79	.58
Informal collaboration	Please indicate how you rate the following statements for your school.				
	Teachers work very closely together in the development and implementation of digitally supported lessons (e.g., joint projects and timing of lesson content).	2.60	1.13	.68	.63
	We have very intensive discussions about our experiences regarding the possible uses of digital technologies.	2.98	1.14	.68	.63
	Teachers are also well informed about the ICT use of colleagues from other schools.	2.34	1.07	.74	.58
Goal clarity	Please indicate how you rate the following statements for your school				
	I am very clear about my school's goals for the use of digital technologies.	3.48	1.11	.72	.55
	The pedagogical and didactic ideas in the teaching staff regarding the use of digital media can be easily reduced to a common denominator.	2.68	1.10	.64	.63
	The colleagues at my school are committed to common goals use of digital media.	2.84	1.19	.67	.60
Strategic importance	Please indicate how you rate the following statements for your school				
	The topic of digitalization is of great importance at our school.	4.01	1.01	.70	.65
	It is highly emphasized in our school that teachers engage in further education activities regarding ICT.	3.71	1.11	.64	.70
	High engagement in furthering ICT use in teaching is well regarded among teacher colleagues.	3.25	1.06	.80	.55

Data availability

The data of this study will be publicly available two years after the end of the project.

References

- Afshari, M., Bakar, K. A., Luan, W. S., Samah, B. A., & Fooi, F. S. (2009). Technology and school leadership. *Technology, Pedagogy and Education*, 18(2), 235–248. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14759390902992527>
- Anderson, M. (2017). Transformational leadership in education: A review of existing literature. *International Social Science Review*, 93(1), 1–13.
- Arokiasamy, A. R. A., bin Abdullah, A. G. K., & Ismail, A. (2015). Correlation between cultural perceptions, leadership style and ICT usage by school principals in Malaysia. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 176, 319–332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.478>
- Bass, B. M. (1990). From transactional to transformational leadership: Learning to share the vision. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18(3), 19–31.
- Beverborg, A. O. G., Slegers, P. J., Endedijk, M. D., & Van Veen, K. (2015). Towards sustaining levels of reflective learning: How do transformational leadership, task interdependence, and self-efficacy shape teacher learning in schools? *Societies*, 5, 187–219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc5010187>
- Blau, I., & Shamir-Inbal, T. (2017). Digital competences and long-term ICT integration in school culture: The perspective of elementary school leaders. *Education and Information Technologies*, 22, 769–787. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-015-9456-7>
- Brown, T. A. (2015). *Confirmatory factor analysis for applied research*. Guilford Publications.
- Brown, W., & May, D. (2012). Organizational change and development: The efficacy of transformational leadership training. *The Journal of Management Development*, 31(6), 520–536.
- Carless, S. A., Wearing, A. J., & Mann, L. (2000). A short measure of transformational leadership. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 14, 389–405.
- Cattaneo, A., Schmitz, M. L., Gonon, P., Antonietti, C., Consoli, T., & Petko, D. (2025). The role of personal and contextual factors when investigating technology integration in general and vocational education. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 163, 108475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2024.108475>
- Chen, W. (2013). School leadership in ICT implementation: Perspectives from Singapore. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 22, 301–311. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-012-0055-8>

- Chiu, T. K. F. (2022). School learning support for teacher technology integration from a self-determination theory perspective. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 70(3), 931–949. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-022-10096-x>
- Cohen, J. (1992). Quantitative methods in psychology: A power primer. *Psychological Bulletin*, 112, 1155–1159.
- Cohrs, C., Bormann, K. C., Diebig, M., Millhoff, C., Pachocki, K., & Rowold, J. (2020). Transformational leadership and communication: Evaluation of a two-day leadership development program. *The Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 41(1), 101–117. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-02-2019-0097>
- Consoli, T., Désiron, J., & Cattaneo, A. (2023). What is “technology integration” and how is it measured in K-12 education? A systematic review of survey instruments from 2010 to 2021. *Computers & Education*, 197, 104742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104742>
- Curran, P. J., West, S. G., & Finch, J. F. (1996). The robustness of test statistics to nonnormality and specification error in confirmatory factor analysis. *Psychological Methods*, 1(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1082-989X.1.1.16>
- Daniëls, E., Hondeghem, A., & Dochy, F. (2019). A review on leadership and leadership development in educational settings. *Educational Research Review*, 27, 110–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2019.02.003>
- De Jong, L., Meirink, J., & Admiraal, W. (2022). School-based collaboration as a learning context for teachers: A systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 112, Article 101927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2022.101927>
- Derue, D. S., Nahrgang, J. D., Wellman, N. E. D., & Humphrey, S. E. (2011). Trait and behavioral theories of leadership: An integration and meta-analytic test of their relative validity. *Personnel Psychology*, 64(1), 7–52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2010.01201.x>
- Dexter, S. (2008). Leadership for IT in schools. *International handbook of information technology in primary and secondary education*. Springer.
- Dexter, S. (2018). The role of leadership for information technology in education: Systems of practices. In J. Voogt, G. Knezek, R. Christensen, & K. W. Lai (Eds.), *Second handbook of information technology in primary and secondary education*. Springer international handbooks of education (pp. 483–498). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-71054-9_32
- Dexter, S., & Richardson, J. W. (2020). What does technology integration research tell us about the leadership of technology? *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 52(1), 17–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2019.1668316>
- Divaharan, S., & Ping, L. C. (2010). Secondary school socio-cultural context influencing ICT integration: A case study approach. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 26(6), 741–763.
- Eickelmann, B. (2011). Supportive and hindering factors to a sustainable implementation of ICT in schools. *Journal for Educational Research Online*, 3(1), 75–103. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:4683>
- Fernandes, P., da Costa, C. A. D. J., & Piedade, S. D. R. (2022). The role of professional collaboration mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction. *Timor Leste Journal of Business and Management*, 4, 53–63.
- Fisher, D. M., & Waller, L. R. (2013). The 21st century principal: A study of technology leadership and technology integration in Texas K-12 schools. *The Global ELearning Journal*, 2(4), 1–44.
- Fullan, M. (1994). Coordinating top-down and bottom-up strategies for educational reform. *Systemic reform: Perspectives on personalizing education*.
- García Torres, D. (2019). Distributed leadership, professional collaboration, and teachers' job satisfaction in US schools. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 79, 111–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.12.001>
- García-Martínez, I., Montenegro-Rueda, M., Molina-Fernandez, E., & Fernández-Batanero, J. M. (2021). Mapping teacher collaboration for school success. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 32(4), 631–649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2021.1925700>
- Garson, G. D. (2009). *Structural equation modeling example using WinAMOS: The Wheaton study*.
- Gelman, A. (2007). Struggles with survey weighting and regression modeling. *Statistical Science*, 22(2), 153–164. <https://doi.org/10.1214/088342306000000691>
- Ghadi, M. Y., Fernando, M., & Caputi, P. (2013). Transformational leadership and work engagement: The mediating effect of meaning in work. *The Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 34(6), 532–550. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-10-2011-0110>
- Gillet, N., Fouquereau, E., Bonnaud-Antignac, A., Mokoukolo, R., & Colombat, P. (2013). The mediating role of organizational justice in the relationship between transformational leadership and nurses' quality of work life: A cross-sectional questionnaire survey. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 50(10), 1359–1367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2012.12.012>
- Goddard, R., Goddard, Y., Sook Kim, E., & Miller, R. (2015). A theoretical and empirical analysis of the roles of instructional leadership, teacher collaboration, and collective efficacy beliefs in support of student learning. *American Journal of Education*, 121(4), 501–530.
- Guggemos, J., & Seufert, S. (2021). Teaching with and teaching about technology—Evidence for professional development of in-service teachers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115, Article 106613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106613>
- Gumus, S., Bulut, O., & Bellibas, M. S. (2013). The relationship between principal leadership and teacher collaboration in Turkish primary schools: A multilevel analysis. *Education Research & Perspectives*, 40(2013), 1–29.
- Hadjithoma-Garstka, C. (2011). The role of the principal's leadership style in the implementation of ICT policy. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 42(2), 311–326. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2009.01014.x>
- Häkansson Lindqvist, M. (2019). School leaders' practices for innovative use of digital technologies in schools. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 50(3), 1226–1240. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12782>
- Hallinger, P. (2003). Leading educational change: Reflections on the practice of instructional and transformational leadership. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 33(3), 329–352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764032000122005>
- Harder, A., Imboden, S., Glassey-Previdoli, D., & Schumann, S. (2020). Schulleitungshandeln in Zeiten der digitalen Transformation - "Business as usual" oder "Alles ist neu". In K. Heinrichs, K. Kögler, & C. Siegfried (Eds.), *Berufliches Lehren und Lernen: Grundlagen, Schwerpunkte und Impulse wirtschaftspädagogischer Forschung*. *Digitale Festschrift für Eveline Wuttke zum 60* (pp. 1–17). Geburtstag https://www.bwpat.de/profil6_wuttke/harder_et_al_profil6.pdf.
- Hargreaves, A. (2021). Teacher collaboration: 30 years of research on its nature, forms, limitations and effects. *Policy, Teacher Education and the Quality of Teachers and Teaching*, 103–121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2019.1639499>
- Hatlevik, I. K., & Hatlevik, O. E. (2018a). Examining the relationship between teachers' ICT self-efficacy for educational purposes, collegial collaboration, lack of facilitation and the use of ICT in teaching practice. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 935. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00935>
- Hatlevik, I. K. R., & Hatlevik, O. E. (2018b). Students' evaluation of digital information: The role teachers play and factors that influence variability in teacher behaviour. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 83, 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2018.01.022>
- Hauge, T. E., & Norenes, S. O. (2015). Collaborative leadership development with ICT: Experiences from three exemplary schools. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 18(3), 340–364. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2014.963689>
- Hu, L., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1–55.
- Imboden, S., Schumann, S., & Conrad, M. (2020). Leitungshandeln an beruflichen Schulen. Eine empirische Bestandsaufnahme und Wege zur Förderung. *Zeitschrift für Pädagogik*, 66(5), 699–726. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:25810>
- Inan, F. A., & Lowther, D. L. (2010). Factors affecting technology integration in K-12 classrooms: A path model. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 58, 137–154. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-009-9132-y>
- Kelloway, K. E., Barling, J., & Helleur, J. (2000). Enhancing transformational leadership: The roles of training and feedback. *The Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 21(3), 145–149. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730010325022>
- Kish, L., & Frankel, M. R. (1974). Inference from complex samples. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B*, 36(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2517-6161.1974.tb00981.x>
- Krein, U. (2023). What's your take on school leadership and digitalization? A systematic review of publications from the last 20 years. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2023.2237939>
- Lambrech, J., Lenkeit, J., Hartmann, A., Ehlert, A., Knigge, M., & Spörer, N. (2022). The effect of school leadership on implementing inclusive education: How transformational and instructional leadership practices affect individualised education planning. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 26(9), 943–957. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2020.1752825>

- Laoui, N. (2020). An investigation into the relationship between principals' leadership styles and level of technology integration in Moroccan public schools. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2020.1799436>
- Laschou, S., Kollias, V., & Karasavvidis, I. (2018). How do transformational principals view ICT as a means for promoting educational innovations? A descriptive case study focusing on twenty-first century skills. *Research on E-Learning and ICT in Education: Technological, Pedagogical and Instructional Perspectives*, 43–67.
- Little, T. D., Rhemtulla, M., Gibson, K., & Schoemann, A. M. (2013). Why the items versus parcels controversy needn't be one. *Psychological Methods*, 18(3), 285. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033266>
- Liu, Y., Bellibağ, M.Ş., & Gümtiş, S. (2021). The effect of instructional leadership and distributed leadership on teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction: Mediating roles of supportive school culture and teacher collaboration. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 49(3), 430–453. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143220910438>
- Liu, S., Keeley, J. W., Sui, Y., & Sang, L. (2021). Impact of distributed leadership on teacher job satisfaction in China: The mediating roles of teacher autonomy and teacher collaboration. *Studies In Educational Evaluation*, 71, Article 101099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2021.101099>
- Lorenz, R., Endberg, M., & Bos, W. (2019). Predictors of fostering students' computer and information literacy—analysis based on a representative sample of secondary school teachers in Germany. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24(1), 911–928. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-018-9809-0>
- Lucas, S. E., & Valentine, J. W. (2002). *Transformational leadership: Principals, leadership teams, and school culture*. New Orleans, LA, USA: Annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association [Paper presentation].
- Marsh, H. W., Lüdtke, O., Nagengast, B., Morin, A. J. S., & Davier, M. von (2013). Why item parcels are (almost) never appropriate: Two wrongs do not make a right—camouflaging misspecification with item parcels in CFA models. *Psychological Methods*, 18(3), 257. [10.1037/a0033266](https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033266)[10.1037/a0032773](https://doi.org/10.1037/a0032773).
- Maxwell, S. E., & Cole, D. A. (2007). Bias in cross-sectional analyses of longitudinal mediation. *Psychological Methods*, 12(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0033266>[10.1037/1082-989X.12.1.23](https://doi.org/10.1037/1082-989X.12.1.23)
- McNeish, D. (2017). Multilevel mediation with small samples: A cautionary note on the multilevel structural equation modeling framework. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 24(4), 609–625. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705511.2017.1280797>
- Meinck, S. (2015). Computing sampling weights in large-scale assessments in education. *Survey methods: Insights from the field*. <https://doi.org/10.13094/SMIF-2015-000>
- Miranda, H., & Russell, M. (2011). Predictors of teacher-directed student use of technology in elementary classrooms: A multilevel SEM approach using data from the USEIT study. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 43(4), 301–323.
- Mon, C. C., Dali, M. H., & Sam, L. C. (2016). Implementation of lesson study as an innovative professional development model among Malaysian school teachers. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction*, 13(1), 83–111.
- Mora-Ruano, J. G., Schurig, M., & Wittmann, E. (2021). Instructional leadership as a vehicle for teacher collaboration and student achievement. What the German PISA 2015 sample tells us. *Frontiers in Education*, 6, Article 582773. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.582773>
- Munir, F., Nielsen, K., & Carneiro, I. G. (2010). Transformational leadership and depressive symptoms: A prospective study. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 120(1–3), 235–239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2009.03.020>
- Ng, W. L. (2008). Transformational leadership and the integration of information and communications technology into teaching. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 17(1), 1–14.
- Ng Foo Seong, D., & Ho, J. M. (2012). How leadership for an ICT reform is distributed within a school. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 26(6), 529–549. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513541211251370>
- Ninković, S., Florić, O. K., & Momčilović, M. (2023). Multilevel analysis of the effects of principal support and innovative school climate on the integration of technology in learning activities. *Computers & Education*, Article 104833. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104833>
- Ninković, S., Knežević-Florić, O., & Đorđić, D. (2022). Transformational leadership and teachers' use of differentiated instruction in Serbian schools: Investigating the mediating effects of teacher collaboration and self-efficacy. *Educational Studies*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2022.2081787>
- Oberski, D. (2014). lavaan: survey: An R package for complex survey analysis of structural equation models. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 57, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v057.i01>
- Ottestad, G. (2013). School leadership for ICT and teachers' use of digital tools. *Nordic Journal of Digital Literacy*, 8(1–2), 107–125. <https://doi.org/10.18261/ISSN1891-943X-2013-01-02-07>
- Petko, D., Egger, N., Cantieni, A., & Wespi, B. (2015). Digital media adoption in schools: Bottom-up, top-down, complementary or optional? *Computers & Education*, 84, 49–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.12.019>
- Petko, D., Prasse, D., & Cantieni, A. (2018). The interplay of school readiness and teacher readiness for educational technology integration: A structural equation model. *Computers in the Schools*, 35(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07380569.2018.1428007>
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Moorman, R. H., & Fetter, R. (1990). Transformational leader behaviors and their effects on followers' trust in leader, satisfaction, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 1(2), 107–142.
- Prasse, D. (2012). Bedingungen innovative Handelns in Schulen. *Funktion und Interaktion von Innovationsbereitschaft, Innovationsklima und Akteursnetzwerken am Beispiel der IKT-Integration an Schulen*. Waxmann Verlag [Doctoral dissertation, Berlin University].
- Reeves, P. M., Pun, W. H., & Chung, K. S. (2017). Influence of teacher collaboration on job satisfaction and student achievement. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, 227–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.06.016>
- Ruloff, M., & Petko, D. (2021). School principals' educational goals and leadership styles for digital transformation: results from case studies in upper secondary schools. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 28(2), 422–440. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2021.2014979>
- Scheel, T. E., Otto, K., Vahle-Hinz, T., Holstad, T., & Rigotti, T. (2019). A fair share of work: Is fairness of task distribution a mediator between transformational leadership and follower emotional exhaustion? *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 2690. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-021-00185-w>
- Schmitz, M. L., Antonietti, C., Consoli, T., Cattaneo, A., Gonon, P., & Petko, D. (2023). Transformational leadership for technology integration in schools: Empowering teachers to use technology in a more demanding way. *Computers & Education*, 204, 104880. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104880>
- Schrum, L., & Levin, B. B. (2013). Leadership for twenty-first-century schools and student achievement: Lessons learned from three exemplary cases. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 16(4), 379–398. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2013.767380>
- Seyal, A. H. (2015). Examining the role of transformational leadership in technology adoption: Evidence from Bruneian technical & vocational establishments (TVE). *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(8), 32–43.
- Stapleton, L. M., McNeish, D. M., & Yang, J. S. (2016). Multilevel and single-level models for measured and latent variables when data are clustered. *Educational Psychologist*, 51(3–4), 317–330. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2016.1207178>
- Tan, S. C. (2010). School technology leadership: Lessons from empirical research. In C. H. Steel, M. J. Keppell, P. Gerbic, & S. Housego (Eds.), *Curriculum, technology & transformation for an unknown future. Proceedings Ascilite Sydney 2010* (pp. 896–906).
- Truijfen, K. J., Slegers, P. J., Meelissen, M. R., & Nieuwenhuis, A. F. M. (2013). What makes teacher teams in a vocational education institution context effective? A qualitative study of managers' view on team working. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 25(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13665621311288485>
- Tulowitzki, P., Gerick, J., & Eickelmann, B. (2022). The role of ICT for school leadership and management activities: An international comparison. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 36(2), 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-06-2021-0251>
- Valckx, J., Vanderlinde, R., & Devos, G. (2020). Departmental PLCs in secondary schools: The importance of transformational leadership, teacher autonomy, and teachers' self-efficacy. *Educational Studies*, 46(3), 282–301. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2019.1584851>
- van Beveren, P., Dimas, I. D., Lourenço, P. R., & Rebelo, T. (2017). Psychometric properties of the Portuguese version of the global transformational leadership (GTL) scale. *Revista de Psicología Del Trabajo Y De Las Organizaciones*, 33(2), 109–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rpto.2017.02.004>
- Vangrieken, K., Dochy, F., Raes, E., & Kyndt, E. (2015). Teacher collaboration: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 15, 17–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.04.002>
- Vermeulen, M., Kreijns, K., van Buuren, H., & van Acker, F. (2017). The role of transformative leadership, ICT-infrastructure and learning climate in teachers' use of digital learning materials during their classes. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 48(6), 1427–1440. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12478>

- Vermeulen, M., van Acker, F., Kreijns, K., & van Buuren, H. (2015). Does transformational leadership encourage teachers' use of digital learning materials. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 43(6), 1006–1025. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143214535749>
- Voelkel, J. R. H. (2022). Causal relationship among transformational leadership, professional learning communities, and teacher collective efficacy. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 25(3), 345–366. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2019.1690699>
- Weddle, H. (2022). Approaches to studying teacher collaboration for instructional improvement: A review of literature. *Educational Research Review*, 35, Article 100415. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2021.100415>
- Winship, C., & Radbill, L. (1994). Sampling weights and regression analysis. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 23(2), 230–257. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049124194023002004>
- Yamamoto, Y., & Yamaguchi, S. (2019). Relationships between ICT implementation at schools and factors related to transformational leadership: A case of primary school in Mongolia. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology*, 15(2), 45–61.
- Yuen, A. H. K., Law, N., & Wong, K. C. (2003). ICT implementation and school leadership: Case studies of ICT integration in teaching and learning. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 41(2), 158–170. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578230310464666>
- Zigler, C. K., & Ye, F. (2019). A comparison of multilevel mediation modeling methods: Recommendations for applied researchers. *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, 54(3), 338–359. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00273171.2018.1527676>